

ROLE OF MAGNESIUM TRACE ELEMENT IN BLOOD SERUM IN DIAGNOSTICS OF UNDIFFERENTIATED CONNECTIVE TISSUE DYSPLASIA

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Abstract. *Connective tissue dysplasia is a modern problem in different fields of medicine. In connective tissue dysplasia, collagen synthesis or metabolism is impaired. Due to impaired collagen synthesis, the strength of connective tissue is reduced. In addition, in connective tissue dysplasia, there is a deficiency of magnesium ions in substrates. Because magnesium is involved in the synthesis of fibrous structures of connective tissue. Thus, the indices of magnesium ions content in blood can be considered as a diagnostic method.*

Keywords: *magnesium, undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia, phenotypic signs, hypercatabolism, deficiency.*

Introduction. Connective tissue dysplasia (CTD) is a common genetic condition that is based on a disorder of collagen type 2 synthesis and hypercatabolism. It is a condition that has various phenotypic and multi-organ manifestations, is characterised by metabolic features and is a specific condition for the development of inflammatory, autoimmune, degenerative changes in various organs. [1,2]. Now many scientists believe that, connective tissue dysplasia is considered as a disorder of connective tissue structure in antenatal and postnatal periods due to genetically altered fibrillogenesis of extracellular matrix, which leads to homeostasis disorder at tissue, organ, organismal levels with a progressive course [2, 9, 10]. Currently, more than 200 types of hereditary pathology have been found, which is based on the disorder of connective tissue metabolism.

Modern science considers connective tissue as a set of different types of tissues united by common origin and structure. It makes up about 50% of the total body weight, forms the supporting framework (skeleton), external coverings, tendons, cartilage, ligaments, organ stroma, and also forms the internal environment of the organism, through which all structural elements receive nutrients and give away metabolic products [3]. Connective tissue is divided into connective tissue proper, cartilage and bone tissue. Connective tissue proper, in turn, is divided into fibrous tissue and connective tissue with special properties. The latter includes reticular, fatty, pigmented and mucous tissues. Fibrous connective tissue, depending on the content of fibrous structures can be loose and dense. Dense connective tissue is characterised by the prevalence of fibrous structures, primarily collagen fibres, the orientation of which in space determines the division of fibrous connective tissue into shaped and unshaped. Loose connective tissue consists of cells and intercellular substance. Cellular elements of loose connective tissue include fibroblasts, macrophages, plasmocytes, tissue basophils, adipocytes, pigmentocytes, adventitia cells, and leukocytes that migrate from the blood [4].

Intercellular substance consists of fibrous structures (collagen, elastic, reticular fibres) and basic substance. The basic (amorphous) substance is represented by water, proteins, lipids, polysaccharides, mineral substances (Mg, Ca, K, Na). One of the main types of connective tissue fibres is collagen fibres, which consist mainly of collagen, a fibrillar protein that is the main

component of the extracellular matrix of connective tissue. Currently, 20 types of collagen are known [5]. Collagen synthesis is encoded by certain genes (there are 50 of them in the human genome) [6].

Among the electrolytes present in the human body, Mg ranks fourth after calcium (Ca), sodium and potassium in terms of its content in blood serum, and second after potassium in terms of its content inside the cell. In the body, Mg content is unevenly distributed: up to 60% of its total amount is in bone tissue, dentin and enamel of teeth; 20% - in tissues with high metabolic activity (heart, muscles, liver, kidneys); up to 20% - in the brain and nervous tissue. About 75% of serum Mg is ionised Mg, 22% is bound to albumin and 3% to globulin. Less than 10% of Mg is in the intercellular space, 0.5% in erythrocytes, and 0.3% in plasma. Cells contain approximately 39% of Mg stores, with 80-90% of the intracellular fraction bound to ATP, distributed in mitochondria (30%), in the cytosol (50%), and in the cell nucleus (10%).

Mg is involved in the synthesis and degradation of nucleic acids, synthesis of proteins, fatty acids and lipids (in particular, phospholipids), and controls the synthesis of cyclic AMP [11,12]. The general effect of Mg²⁺ on any tissue is that Mg²⁺ ions are required for stabilisation of non-coding RNAs. Specifically, Mg²⁺ ion stabilises the structure of transport RNA (tRNA), and Mg²⁺ deficiency leads to an increase in the number of dysfunctional tRNA molecules, reducing and slowing the overall rate of protein synthesis. Mg content directly affects the activity of enzymes such as metalloproteinases, hyaluronidase, hyaluron synthetase, lysyl oxidase, and transglutaminase, which in turn regulate the rate of synthesis of various proteins. Disturbance of Ca/Mg ratio in case of Mg deficiency leads to an increase in the activity of metalloproteinases that promote collagen degradation with a decrease in its synthesis [13].

The expression of another ion transporter gene SLC41A1 (solute transporter type 41.1) also increases in hypomagnesaemia: In an experiment in mice on a magnesium-free diet, mRNA expression of the SLC41A1 gene is increased in kidney, intestine and heart [14].

The magnesium and calcium metabolism is regulated by the magnesium-sensitive plasma membrane receptor (CASR gene), which is expressed in the parathyroid gland and renal tubules. Due to its high sensitivity to small changes in circulating calcium and magnesium concentrations, CASR acts as a sensor (transducer) responsive to cation concentration and plays an essential role in maintaining cation homeostasis [15].

The most general effect of magnesium on any tissue is that magnesium ions are required to stabilise non-coding RNAs. Magnesium deficiency leads to an increase in the number of dysfunctional tRNA molecules, thus reducing and slowing down the overall rate of protein synthesis. In addition to tRNAs, magnesium also stabilises small nuclear RNAs (so-called snRNAs) [16]. Consequently, magnesium deficiency in connective tissue will lead to a slowdown in the synthesis of all structural molecules (including proteoglycans, glycosaminoglycans, collagens and elastin). As the synthesis of structural molecules so essential for the repair of connective tissue is slowed down, repair processes are also inhibited, and this leads to a deterioration in the mechanical characteristics of the tissue. Magnesium ions can modulate the activity of the corresponding biosynthetic enzymes. For example, hyaluronan synthetases HAS1, HAS2 and HAS3 contain a magnesium ion in the active centre. It is also known that the action of hyaluronidase inhibitors (enzymes that degrade hyaluronan) depends on the concentration of magnesium ions [17]. Thus, magnesium deficiency can lead to a decrease in the activity of hyaluronan synthetases and at the same time to an increase in the activity of hyaluronidases (since inhibitors cease to act in magnesium deficiency). Both of these processes will lead to deterioration

of the mechanical properties of hyaluronan filaments and partial degradation of the amorphous substance that forms the basis of the extracellular matrix.

The effects of magnesium on connective tissue are not limited to collagen and collagenases. Microfibrils and elastin are the main components of elastic fibres. Degradation of elastin fibres can increase significantly (2-3 fold) in the presence of magnesium [18].

Magnesium deficiency contributes to lower activity of elastases and higher concentration of elastic fibres. Transglutaminase, an enzyme that forms glutamine-lysine cross-links that link elastin chains together, is activated by calcium and inhibited by magnesium [19,20]. Magnesium can inhibit copper-dependent lysyl oxidase (LOX) [21], also involved in cross-linking of elastin and/or collagen chains. Consequently, magnesium deficiency can lead to activation of cross-linking of collagens and elastins, and this process, along with an increase in MMP activity, will lead to a kind of granularisation of connective tissue, stratification into 'laminae' consisting of half degraded collagen molecules, which as a result leads to a decrease in mechanical strength.

Thus, the available data allow us to conclude that the most probable mechanisms of magnesium deficiency impact on connective tissue are: 1) increased degradation of collagen fibres, 2) synthesis of defective collagen due to disruption of the structure and assembly of collagen fibres, 3) disruption of the ratio of collagen and elastic fibres towards an increase in the latter, 4) slowing down the synthesis of all structural molecules of connective tissue. Consequently, magnesium plays an essential role in the formation of the normal structure of connective tissue, and disruption of magnesium homeostasis is one of the etiological factors in the formation of connective tissue dysplasia. At present, many phenotypic signs of DST and microanomalies have been identified, which can be divided into external, determined by physical examination, and internal, i.e. signs of DST on the part of internal organs and the central nervous system. Every year the number of registrations of microanomalies and morphogenetic variants in children increases, which, unlike malformations, are located near the boundaries of variants of the normal structure of organs and slightly impair their functions. The most characteristic external phenotypic features of DST include [1-3]: dolichocephaly, skull asymmetry; epicanthus, narrow eye slits, radial lacunar type of iris, blue sclerae; ear asymmetry, low position of the ears, protruding ears, small or appressed lobes, irregular shape of the curls, Darwin's tubercle, absence of the goiter; 'gothic' palate, ability to roll the tongue into a tube; bite anomalies, growth of teeth outside the dental row, multiple caries; chest deformities (funnel-shaped, keel-shaped, flat), hypomastia; scoliosis, smoothing of thoracic kyphosis, increased lumbar lordosis; short or crooked little fingers, thickening of nail phalanges, IV finger longer than II, wrist sign, Healy O-shaped curvature of legs, II toe longer than I, 'sandal-shaped' 1st intertarsal cleft of the foot; ability to bring I finger to the forearm, overextension of V metacarpophalangeal joint.

Visceral markers of DST are [1-3]: 1) cardiovascular system: (a) Atria and interatrial septum - prolapsing inferior vena cava valve, enlarged eustachian flap greater than 10 mm, open oval window, small aneurysm of the interatrial septum, abnormal trabeculae in the right atrium, prolapsing crest muscles in the right atrium; b) tricuspid valve - displacement of the septal flap into the right ventricular cavity within 10 mm, dilatation of the right atrioventricular orifice, prolapsed tricuspid valve; c) pulmonary artery - dilatation of the pulmonary artery trunk, prolapsed pulmonary valve flaps; d) aorta - borderline narrow aortic root, borderline wide aortic root, dilatation of the sinus of Valsalva, bicuspid aortic valve, asymmetry of the aortic valve flaps, prolapse of the aortic valve flaps; e) left ventricle - deformation of the ventricular outflow tract with a systolic roll in the upper third of the interventricular septum, longitudinal trabecula in the

left ventricular cavity, transverse trabecula in the left ventricular cavity, diagonal trabecula in the left ventricular cavity, small aneurysm of the interventricular septum; e) mitral valve - mitral valve prolapse, ectopic attachment of the chords of the anterior valve leaflet, ectopic attachment of the chords of the posterior valve leaflet, disturbed distribution of the chords of the anterior valve leaflet, disturbed distribution of the chords of the posterior valve leaflet, additional groups of papillary muscles, abnormal location of the base of the papillary muscles; 2) bronchopulmonary system: Polycystic lung disease, primary pulmonary emphysema, spontaneous pneumothorax, tracheobronchial dyskinesia; 3) digestive system: visceroptosis, gallbladder deformity and/or hypotension, Bauhinia flap insufficiency; 4) genitourinary system: nephroptosis, kidney and/or urinary tract atopy, genital anomaly [22].

Materials and Methods. The study was conducted in the clinic of TashPMI in the reception department among 115 children aged 5 to 15 years. These children had signs of undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia such as: asthenic physique, skull asymmetry, bite abnormalities, posture disorders, joint hypermobility, 'O' or 'X' shaped curvature of legs, visible venous network. In addition, visceral signs: mitral valve prolapse, biliary dyskinesia and various anomalies of other organs. The material for the study was venous blood taken from these patients. The method of determination of magnesium is - photometric analysis. The norm is from 0.6 mmol/l to 1.1 mmol/l (or from 1.46 mg/dl to 2.68 mg/dl).

Study Results. Fifty-eight per cent (67) of the sick children had values below normal (0.2-0.5 mmol/l). In 37% (42) patients, the results showed low borderline normal (0.6-0.7 mmol/l). And in 5% (6) of patients the values were within the normal range (0.9-1.1 mmol/l).

Conclusions. Our study showed that patients with phenotypic and visceral signs of undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia have a deficiency of the trace element magnesium. So, low concentration of magnesium in blood we can take as a laboratory indicator of connective tissue dysplasia and it should be taken into account when drawing up a treatment plan.

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